

Efficient Extraction Techniques for Bioanalysis : A Review of Current Methodologies

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ABSTRACT

Bioanalytical methods are commonly employed to quantify pharmaceuticals and their metabolites in plasma matrices and they play an essential part in toxicokinetic, pharmacokinetic, and pharmacodynamics research estimate and interpretation. Sample preparation is considered as the bottleneck step in bioanalysis because each biological matrix has its own unique challenges and complexity, to ensure high reliability, sensitivity, selectivity and reproducibility of an analytical method. This paper reviews the recent developments in bioanalysis sample preparation techniques and gives an update on modern trends in bioanalytical sample preparation techniques, including sorbent-based microextraction techniques, are primarily emphasized. Conventional liquid-liquid extraction (LLE), protein precipitation (PP) and solid-phase extraction (SPE) techniques are now been considered as methods of the past.

KEY WORDS: Bioanalysis, Biological matrices, Sample Preparation Techniques,

Micro extraction ,Solid Phase Extraction.

INTRODUCTION

The development of bioanalytical sample preparation techniques has become challenging over the decades because of the need to constantly accomplish higher sensitivity, accuracy, and speed of analysis in complex biofluids (e.g., blood, serum, plasma, saliva, faeces, and urine).(1) The main objective of sample preparation process is to provide a suitable sample, usually for chromatographic analysis, which will not contaminate the instrumentation and where the concentration in the prepared sample is reflective of that found in the original. The method of sample preparation selected is generally dictated by the analytical technique available and the physical characteristics of the analytes under investigation(2).

Sample preparation is necessary for at least two reasons(10).

- a. To remove as many of the endogenous interferences from the analyte as possible.
- b. To enrich the sample with respect to the analyte, thus maximizing the sensitivity of the system.

It also serves to ensure that the injection matrix is compatible with the selected column and mobile phase. In simple terms, sample preparation is a process which aims at selective isolation of the analyte of interest from the matrix, minimization/elimination of matrix components in the processed sample and, if required, concentration of the analyte of interest.

Extraction techniques in bioanalysis

- **Protein Precipitation**

Principle: It depends on the solubility of analyte in particular solvent present in biological matrix i.e., blood, plasma, serum.

Solvent used: Methanol, ACN etc. It is basically denaturing the proteins. Precipitation of proteins can be done by using any one of the methods mentioned below:

By changing the pH of sample- by mixing inorganic reagents like Perchloric acid, Trichloroacetic acid etc. In isoelectric pH, proteins have no net charge, which causes insolubility thus precipitates(1).

By addition of organic solvents- It decreases the dielectric constant of the medium, leads to insolubility thus cause precipitation, in another case high affinity for the hydrophobic surfaces of the protein leads to denaturing of proteins. Example: Methanol, Acetonitrile etc.

By addition of Salts - salts used for precipitation of proteins are citrates, phosphates, acetates, etc.

Protein precipitation plates

One of the recent approaches to eliminating the disadvantages of the conventional manual PP method is development of membrane-based PP filter plates. PP plates have been developed so that, after precipitation of protein, filtration can be carried out in the same well without centrifugation and supernatant transfer steps. PP plates when compared with manual PP, offers several advantages such as, reduced processing time, Higher solvent recovery(2).

Fig No:01 Protein Precipitation

- **Liquid Liquid Extraction**

Principle: It is based on selective extraction of intended analyte present in liquid sample through immiscible organic solvent.

Solvent used: Methyl ter-Butyl Ether (MTBE), Dichloromethane(DCM), Ethyl acetate (EC), Diethyl ether (DEE), Hexane etc.any solvent as individual or in combination with any other suitable solvent can be used as an extraction solvent(1).

Liquid–liquid extraction (LLE) is a technique that consists in the transfer of the target compound from their original medium to a water-immiscible solvent, namely extractant solvent, with which the sample is put in contact during a certain time. The contact between the two immiscible phases is enhanced mechanically, typically by agitation and, less frequently, by (magnetic) stirring or by creating turbulences with a cylinder/piston system. Ideally, an efficient LLE will transfer quantitatively the target analytes to the extractant solvent, maintaining the potential interfering substances and particulate material in the aqueous phase, which is discarded. The water-organic phase partition coefficient of the target compound is the main parameter that rules this process(8).

Fig no:02 LLE

- **Solid-phase Extraction Technique**

Principle: It is based on adsorption (or) Partitioning on to solid sorbent (Adsorbent)”. Selective retardation of analyte using solid sorbent under specific condition. SPE is based on the selective adsorption mechanism. If the targeted analyte are adsorbed on the solid phase, they can selectively be removed or eluted by using an appropriate elution solvent⁶. Different cartridges are used in solid phase extraction(3).

Steps involved in SPE:-

1. Conditioning: All SPE tubes are required to be conditioned with appropriate solvents prior to sample application.

2. Sample Application: Application of sample from the top of the cartridge at a slow flow rate without any brake by taking care that no sample drop should remain on the inner wall of the cartridges, slow rate is necessary to allow analyte to interact with adsorbent thus to achieve the retention of analytes because of temporary weak bonding.

3. Rinsing or Washing: It is intended for the removal of matrix components or other interferences by washing the cartridge with relative weak dilute solvent or solvent mixtures or buffer and interferences that are weakly retained than the analytes are drained out from the cartridge. Rinsing or washing solvents are water, buffers of different pH(7).

4. Drying; Drying can be done by applying appropriate vacuum for recommended time period with help of vacuum pump, recommended drying time is 2-3 minutes.

5. Elution: It involves passing of strong solvent through cartridge at a slow flow rate thus allowing more soak time on the packing of reach maximum extraction efficiency, elution solvents are MeOH, ACN, acidic or alkaline MeOH or ACN (7).

Type of SPE:

1. Reversed phase SPE
2. Normal phase SPE
3. Ion exchange SPE

Fig No:03 SPE

- **Micro-extraction by packed sorbent**

Micro-extraction by packed sorbent (MEPS) is a miniature SPE. The purpose of MEPS is to reduce the sorbent bed volume, making it suitable for large sample volume range (from as low as 10–1000 mL), reducing the number of steps typically involved in conventional SPE and providing easy automation. Typical MEPS is designed in the syringe format, wherein approximately 1 mg of the sorbent is packed inside a syringe (100–250 mL) as a plug or between the barrel and the needle as a cartridge (1).

- **Solid phase micro extraction**

A new sample preparation technique using a fused-silica fiber coated on the outside with an appropriate stationary phase and is termed Solid phase micro-extraction (SPME). Physically, it is a modified syringe that contains stainless steel microtubing within its syringe needle. This microtubing has about a 1 cm fused silica fiber tip which is coated with an organic polymer. This coated silica fiber can be moved backwards and forwards with the plunger of the syringe (5). The foremost advantage of the technique is improved detection limits. There are two types of extraction modes for SPME: first, direct immersion (DI) of SPME fiber into liquid sample matrix, simply termed as DI-SPME and second, head-space (HS) extraction in which the liquid sample matrix is heated in a vial to volatilize the analytes and the fiber is placed just above the sample matrix. Various commercially available fiber coatings are polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) for extraction of non-polar analytes, polyacrylate (PA, thickness 85 nm) for extraction of polar analytes (2).

Fig No:04 SPME

- **Magnetic Solid Phase Extraction**

Magnetic solid phase extraction (MSPE) is a new technique that utilizes a magnetic adsorbent to a solution containing a certain analyte. The analyte is adsorbed into the magnetic sorbent and then separated magnetically (10). Finally, the analyte eluted from the recovered adsorbent. It involves the use of magnetic materials, such as magnetic nanoparticles or beads, functionalized with specific ligands that selectively bind to target molecules. The sample is mixed with these magnetic particles, allowing the analytes to be captured. After binding, an external magnet is applied to separate the solid phase from the liquid phase, followed by washing steps to remove impurities. Finally, the analytes are eluted from the magnetic phase for further analysis, such as chromatography or mass spectrometry. MSPE offers high sensitivity, efficiency, and minimal sample preparation(6).

FigNo:05 Magnetic Phase Solid Extraction

- **Super Critical Fluid Extraction**

Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) is an analytical technique that uses a supercritical fluid (typically CO₂) to extract compounds from solid or liquid samples. The principle behind SFE relies on the unique properties of supercritical fluids, which have characteristics of both gases

and liquids. In the supercritical state, these fluids exhibit high diffusivity, low viscosity, and high solubility for a wide range of compounds, allowing efficient extraction(4).

SFE is particularly useful for bioanalysis, as it minimizes sample degradation due to the low temperatures involved and avoids the use of organic solvents, making it more environmentally friendly. Furthermore, it is highly efficient in extracting bioactive compounds such as lipids, alkaloids, and essential oils from biological matrices. The advantages of SFE in bioanalysis include high selectivity, minimal sample preparation, and the ability to handle sensitive or thermolabile substances. Additionally, it offers faster extraction times compared to traditional methods like solvent extraction, making it a valuable tool in modern bioanalytical laboratories(9).

Fig No:06 SFE

- **Disposable pipette extraction**

DPX is an effective sample preparation technique for separation and extraction of analytes from the various matrices. In its simplest original form, it is modified standard pipette tip (1/5mL), which is loaded with free flowing sorbent powder, which is free to disperse. Being a standard tip, it is easy to take the solvent in or out through this dispersive sorbent(9). In its modified form, the standard tip contains a dispersible sorbent loosely placed between two frits (one frit placed on the lower end of the tip through which solvent can be taken up/down and the second placed at the upper end of the tip to avoid solvent contamination in to the pipette). In case of conventional SPE cartridges which contain packed bed sorbent, sample is loaded from the top; every sorbent particle is used once (as sample travels through the bed under gravity), thus much sorbent material is required to retain analytes. Also, the success of conventional SPE depends on

flowcontrol of the sample loading, washing and elution to achieve good repeatabilities. This leads to fast and efficient extractionand not much material needed to retain analytes(3).

Application Of Bioanalytical Strategies

If a sample has been analysed with a separation method theresult will be in form of a chromatogram.(2) The eluting substances will produce signals in the detector separated bytime, creating a pattern of peaks. Calibration curves can beconstructed from a set of samples with different concentrationsand be used for predictions of concentrations in unknownsamples. Area or peak height can be used and the choicedepends upon the situation.The developed Bioanalytical method can be applied for variouspurposes:

a. pharmacokinetic methods

Pharmacokinetic deals with the changes of drug concentration inthe drug product and changes of concentration of a drug and/orits metabolite(s) in the human or animal body followingadministration of the drug product, i.e., the changes of drugconcentration in the different body fluid and tissues in thedynamic system of liberation, absorption, distribution, bodystorage, binding, metabolism, and excretion.Two major pharmacokinetic methods arePlasma level-Time studies and Urinary excretion studies(2).

b. pharmacodynamic studies-

It involves direct measurement of drug effect on a physiologicalprocess as function of time(1).

c. Toxicology and Forensic Science

d.Clinical Diagnostics and Disease Monitoring

Biomarker Detection: Identifying and quantifying biomarkers for the diagnosis of various diseases (e.g., cancers, infections, metabolic disorders).

CONCLUSION

The selection of an extraction technique in bioanalysis is a critical step that impacts the quality of data, efficiency of the process, and cost-effectiveness of the analysis. Factors such as analyte characteristics, sample matrix, sensitivity requirements, and regulatory compliance must be carefully considered to choose the optimal extraction method. Making the wrong choice can lead to poor recovery, interference from matrix effects, inaccurate results, and wasted resources, while a well-chosen method will streamline the analysis process, improve reliability, and ensure valid conclusions. Ultimately, the selection of an extraction method is guided by factors such as the physicochemical properties of the analytes, sample type, matrix complexity, time constraints, and the sensitivity needed for downstream analytical techniques. Advancements in extraction technologies, such as miniaturized and automated systems, continue to enhance the robustness and throughput of bioanalytical processes, enabling more precise and efficient analysis across a broad range of applications in drug development, clinical diagnostics, and environmental monitoring.

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